

SPECIAL PECULIARITIES OF IMPLEMENTATION OF MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' CREATIVE THINKING SKILLS

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Annotation: This article gives information about scientific essence of the development of students' creative thinking skills on the basis of artistic competence, initiation and investigation of a person.

Key words: Thinking, creativity, education, upbringing, competitiveness, attitude, approach, teacher, experimental activity, research.

Increasing the competitiveness of future pedagogic specialists, forming the creative thinking skills of students, psychological and pedagogical influence on the development of creative thinking skills from the student period is a topic that has not been studied much, and it directly reflects the goals of modern education.

Pedagogy consists of researching the psychological foundations of creativity, formation of creativity, creative thinking skills of future teachers in higher education institutions, highlighting the importance of scientific and artistic creativity, pedagogical and psychological diagnosis of students' level of thinking within the framework of creative relations.

Forming the thinking of creative relations in students is considered as following:

- a scientific expression of achieving the goal set as a result of the individual's creative abilities, aspirations, and research.

Focusing on the concept of creativity and its types is appropriate to our investigations.

Creativity is the activity of a person to create new material and spiritual materials. Human thinking, memory, imagination, attention, will actively participate in this process, furthermore all knowledge, experience, talent are shown [1]. Creativity is first born in the imagination of a person, then research is conducted on issues related to creativity; the work done by others is critically reviewed, analyzed; observations and experiments are held; logical conclusions are drawn; hypotheses are made and tested in the experiment; updated if they are wrong, etc.

Scientific research is a process of developing new knowledge, one of the types of cognitive activity. It is characterized by objectivity, reliability, accuracy. Scientific research must always give the same results when it is repeated in all conditions and prove the issue under discussion. Scientific research consists of two interconnected parts: experiment and theory. The main components of scientific research are: definition of the topic, preliminary analysis of available information, conditions and methods in the field of research, scientific hypotheses, experimenting, analysis and generalization of the obtained results, verification of the hypotheses based on the obtained evidence, expression of new facts and laws, scientific predict. It is common to divide scientific research into fundamental and practical, quantitative and qualitative, unique and complex research.[1]

Knowing is the process of understanding reality. Human understanding and knowledge of existence is carried out through four types of cognitive activities: simple, scientific, artistic and religious. Objective knowledge is obtained as a result of scientific research. Students' cognitive activity is carried out in three stages. The first stage of cognitive activity is acquiring knowledge, sensing and perceiving things and events in reality, the second stage is understanding and generalizing knowledge, and the third stage is strengthening and applying it.

The theory of knowledge is a branch of philosophy that studies the problems of knowledge and its possibilities, which is manifested in the relationship between knowledge and reality, as well as the condition of reliability and validity of knowledge.

The concept of activity is a concept that applies only to a person; creativity depends only on activity. For us, the most important thing is to develop the creative thinking skills of students. We believe that algorithmic, heuristic methods of mental activity should be widely used in the processes of developing the creative thinking skills of future teachers. [3]

In the process of research, it was important to distinguish productive (effective) and reproductive types of thinking. Taking into account the signs of creative thinking, we set ourselves the task of distinguishing the features related to the ease of acquiring knowledge and the speed of development. In doing so, we connected concepts related to general abilities.

The most important feature of thinking that distinguishes it from other mental processes is that it is oriented towards the discovery of new knowledge. New knowledge is a lesser-known, unconventional form of knowledge. This is the kind of knowledge we do not mean. The ability of students to independently discover new knowledge is related to the level of development of creative thinking. This kind of thinking is related to the creation of a new model in which the creative thinking skill can be formed in future teachers. First of all, it is related to the extent to which future teachers master and use innovative technologies.

It is crucial to use modern information technologies and non-traditional information sources (hypertext and multimedia systems, constructive environments) in preparing future teachers for the educational process. Besides that, the effective use of computer technologies, which help in the development of students' creative thinking, is also a cause of great interest.

Students who have created the opportunity to effectively use information technologies will form creative thinking skill in the process of education. Today, it is important to apply modern pedagogical technologies during the academic process to the form the creative thinking skills of students.

According to A.I. Prigozhkin, innovation is a new approach to the relationship with a specific social unit - organization, population, society, group, and

the implementation of these relationships is faced with resistance in its own way. But in order to achieve the set goal, every person, a citizen, specialist, leader, employee, and, moreover, a participant in the process of various social relations, must demonstrate innovative competence. [3]

American psychologist E. Rodgers in his researches studied social-psychological aspects of social relations with an innovative character, innovation in social relations, categories of people participating in this process, their attitude to innovation, the level of readiness to accept innovation, understand its essence, and the innovative character of classification of social relations among certain categories of people.

Innovative education (see "innovation" - creation, invention) - education that creates an opportunity for the learner to create new ideas, norms, rules, qualities and skills related to the natural acceptance of advanced ideas, norms, rules created by other people.

The technologies used in the process of innovative education are called innovative educational technologies or educational innovations.

Educational innovations are forms, methods and technologies used in the field of education or in the educational process to solve existing problems based on a new approach and guarantee a more effective result than before.

Educational innovations are also called "innovative education". The concept of "innovative education" was first used in 1979 at the "Club of Rome".

Innovation consists of several forms. The following are the main kinds of innovation:

- new ideas;
- specific goals aimed at changing the system or direction of activity;
- unconventional approaches;
- unusual initiatives;
- advanced working methods.

The aim is to obtain the highest possible results from the spent money and effort in the application of innovations in the educational system or educational activities. Innovation differs from any news in that it must have a changeable mechanism that allows for management and control. That's why innovative approaches are important in the formation of students' creative thinking in educational process.

Reference

1. ЎЗМЭ биринчи жилд .Тошкент, 2000-йил.
2. Саяфназаров И., Мухтаров А., Бобосв А. Илмий тадқиқот методологияси. Ўқув-услубий қўлланма. -Т.: ТДИУ, 2014. -16 бетда.
3. Аллаёрова С.Н.Герменевтика.Тошкент.2017 й.- 9 бет
4. Нововведения. Стимулы и препятствия (Социальные проблемы инноватики) | Пригожин Аркадий Ильич. 1989г